

Towards the first hybrid autophage rocket: early combustion insights

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ABSTRACT: Autophage propulsion is a rarely explored launcher architecture that uses one of its propellants, which must be a solid, as the main structure of the vehicle. This configuration removes the need for tanks and stage interfaces, potentially halving the launcher's dry mass. During flight, the length of the rocket decreases, resulting in a single-stage-to-orbit launcher with simplified design and logistics. The Ambre rocket is the first experimental autophage rocket that Alpha Impulsion aims to launch in 2024. Its thruster comprises a hybrid combustion chamber that resembles classical hybrid rocket engines (HRE). This new architecture requires validation of its components before the autophage configuration is tested. Hence, the HRE tested in this work (1kN, 90%HTP-HDPE) is equipped with representative chamber, nozzle and catalytic injection designs (MnO_2 coated alumina pellets, swirling gas injector) of the Ambre rocket. This preliminary campaign of five firing tests aims to verify the internal combustion performance of the Ambre rocket, its regression rate under swirling flow and its thrust. These parameters were verified at several operating points and the thermal behaviour of the upper part of the chamber was observed – it will become an interface for the sliding grain entering the chamber. This work will continue with the following campaigns in the project, testing the autophage configuration.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

HDPE High Density PolyEthylene
 HRE Hybrid Rocket Engine
 HTP High Test Peroxide
 PP PolyPropylene
 SSTO Single Stage To Orbit

Symbols

\dot{m} Mass flow rate
 \dot{r}_f Fuel regression rate
 A Area
 a Regression rate coefficient
 D Diameter
 G_{ox} Oxidiser mass flux
 L Length
 n Oxidiser flux exponent
 r Chamber radius
 SN_g Geometrical Swirl Number

t Time
 v_a Autophage velocity (feeding rate)
 w Grain thickness

Greek symbols

α Swirl injector outlet angle (from axis)
 $\rho_{ox,liq}$ Oxidiser density in liquid phase
 θ Regression slope angle

Subscripts

b burn
 ch chamber
 end end of the test (flame extinction)
 f fuel
 h heating zone
 hub hub of the axial swirl injector
 in start of the test
 ox oxidiser
 $post$ post-combustion zone
 sw swirl injector

1 INTRODUCTION

Autophage propulsion is a type of chemical propulsion for space transportation, with a significant impact on the architecture of the launch vehicle. The base concept of autophage propulsion was presented in a previous work [1]. It is a Single Stage To Orbit (SSTO) launcher that uses a solid propellant as its structure, removing the need for structural tanks and reducing mass and complexity of the launcher. The launcher shrinks during flight, much like a candle whose flame would be controlled by a rocket engine. The engine is able to climb up the combustible structure as it is consumed. At the end of the flight, only the upper part containing the payload, and this rocket engine, remain.

The state of the art related to autophage propulsion is limited, with only two known on-going projects apart from Alpha Impulsion. An engine using solid propulsion was proposed [2], and recently, University of Glasgow published the results of an experimental study on a Gaseous Oxygen (GOX) and Propane combustion supported by a secondary solid fuel (HDPE) that would be used as the launcher's structure [3].

Hybrid propulsion brings several benefits: green propellants, safety, performance, throttleability and re-ignition. Alpha Impulsion proposed the hybrid autophage launcher concept (see Fig. 1). This implementation proposes to use fuel as the launcher's main body and as the tank for the liquid oxidizer. The launcher is an SSTO with a lighter architecture and a simpler industrial process, with a strong

Fig. 1: Hybrid autophage concept with a lead screw insertion system

potential to reduce costs and environmental impact. Many parts are removed from the design: propellant tanks (typically half the dry mass of classic launchers), half of the fluid systems (compared to bi-liquid propulsion), separation systems and upper stages as a whole. Besides, this simplification tends to decrease the risk of space debris and the wasted mass overall (atmospheric burn or ocean impact). System analysis carried out by the authors indicates that a fully operational autophage mini-launcher would be able to handle twice the payload mass of a classical mini launcher for the same size, and potentially more at larger scales of vehicles [1]. Hence, maturing hybrid autophage propulsion might provide a straightforward path to lower launch costs and environmental impact, by reducing launcher complexity and the primary source of carbon footprint: propellant mass [4]. This theoretical result should be verified by a demonstration vehicle. While this mini-launcher is in the pre-project phase in Alpha Impulsion, preliminary experiments can be done on small scale systems.

No flight prototype was ever tested in any implementation of the autophage propulsion. This is one of the objectives of the Ambre project.

Ambre is a small experimental rocket (1kN thrust, 90%HTP/HDPE). It is set to fly in 2024 to demonstrate autophage flight for the first time. The present work is part of the development of this rocket. Results of the first firing test campaign are reported. Hybrid autophage propulsion relies on three pillars: hybrid combustion applied to sliding grains, propellants insertion system, and mechanics of the launcher structure made of fuel (HDPE for Ambre). In order to reach a flight test, many parameters for the combustion and the insertion need to be verified. This led to the development of a classic hybrid rocket engine and a non-firing insertion test rig separately, to validate components before both are integrated in the rocket. The test campaign presented here addressed combustion aspects. While the insertion system is being developed, the engine configuration is kept as a classic HRE, with a geometry able to be converted to an autophage mode. Hence, several components are present in

their final version, and one goal of this campaign is to verify their behaviour and ensure predictability when testing the autophage mode in the near future. These components are the catalytic bed and swirling injector, the chamber wall and thermal protection, and the nozzle. The insertion system will benefit from these results, which induce constraints on its design.

This article aims to verify the behaviour of these components to ensure that the autophage version of the engine can ignite and burn its sliding grain. It also aims to predict the length of the grain during firing in autophage mode and report observations that influence the development and operation of the autophage engine.

2 MODEL

Considering a single port configuration as in Fig. 1, the autophage combustion chamber is the seat of two balancing effects that control the shape and size of the combustion surface: the propellant feeding rate and the grain regression rate. The propellant feeding rate is referred in this work as autophage velocity \bar{v}_a . The autophage velocity can be described as the relative velocity between the rocket engine and the fuel grain. This parameter is fully controlled by the insertion system - that is stator, rotor, lead screw and free-run stop in Fig. 1. The second element of the balance equation is the regression rate of the fuel grain \dot{r}_f . As the grain is inserted, the combustion on its internal surface causes its thickness to decrease. The combined effect of the regression and the insertion of the fuel creates a conical shape. The size of the conical fuel grain inside the combustion chamber is of paramount importance. Indeed, the design of the combustion chamber must take into account the maximum length of the regressing surface, also referred as regression length L_r . The autophage regression length L_r is defined as the axial distance between the start and the end of the conical grain being regressed inside the chamber. If on one hand the oversizing of the combustion chamber implies additional mass, on the other hand its undersizing exposes the insertion motor to additional loads. The former scenario leads to unnecessary mass, making the benefits of the autophage technology vain, while the latter event might lead to emergency stop of the insertion due to motor overloading. Hence, the importance of predicting L_r is clear.

2.1 Equilibrium Shape of the Burning Grain

A simplification of the grain burning into the combustion chamber at its equilibrium point is reported in Fig. 2. The equilibrium point is defined as the condition at which the regression and the insertion are balanced, causing a steady combustion surface that does not change neither the shape nor the position inside the chamber. The L_r of the conical

Fig. 2: Regression model in the hybrid autophagy engine

fuel at equilibrium can be estimated by using a space-time averaged regression rate \dot{r}_f . The angle of the cone links the velocities and the geometrical parameters of the cone as follows:

$$\sin \theta = \frac{\dot{r}_f}{v_a} \quad (1)$$

$$\tan \theta = \frac{w}{L\dot{r}} \quad (2)$$

A concrete case like Ambre shows that v_a is in the order of $[10^{-2}; 10^{-1}]m/s$ while \dot{r}_f is in the order of $[10^{-4}; 10^{-3}]m/s$. The angle θ formed by the composition of these vectors is then eligible to the small angle approximation. With this assumption it is possible to write:

$$\tan \theta = \frac{\dot{r}_f}{v_a} = \frac{w}{L\dot{r}} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the evaluation of the regression cone at equilibrium can be easily obtained as:

$$L\dot{r}_{,eq} = w \frac{v_a}{\dot{r}_f} \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_{eq} = \arctan\left(\frac{\dot{r}_f}{v_a}\right) \quad (5)$$

2.2 Dynamic Evolution of the Burning Grain Shape

Yet, the equilibrium state is not representative of the dynamic evolution of the burning grain and the variable volume it takes inside the combustion chamber. In order to prevent erroneous combustion chamber designs, it is necessary to estimate the maximum regression length $L_{\dot{r},max}$ that the conical fuel attains during insertion. Therefore, a code to estimate the conical fuel as a function of time during operation has been developed. This tool takes into account (i) the autophagy velocity, (ii) the regression rate and (iii) the initial shape of the grain. The autophagy velocity is an input parameter that depends on operational decisions; its upper limit is dictated by the performance of the electric motor. On the other hand, differently from the simplified equilibrium model, the regression rate spatial dependency can be considered. Instead of the spatial-time averaged \dot{r}_f , the local regression rate $\dot{r}_{f,x}$ is exploited to take into account the variation along

the axial distance from the injector. As for the third parameter, an example of the initial shape of the fuel grain is reported in Fig. 3. The thickness is constrained by external system requirements, while the truncation at the end is driven by practical considerations for the fuel production. The initial shape of the fuel strongly influences the time required to get to the equilibrium condition. For this reason, the slope of the cone is selected to directly match the final conical shape at the equilibrium condition θ_{eq} .

Fig. 3: Initial shape of the grain sliding from left to right. $\bar{x} = 0$ represents the axial position at which the oxidizer is injected

The code reproduces the dynamic process of the fuel grain entering the combustion chamber, in which it faces a regression field. The ignition delay of the fuel makes the grain grow in the combustion chamber without regressing. Once it ignites, the tool simulates the grain shape evolution for the length of the burning time selected. Throughout this period the local regression rate is assumed to be steady.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the experimental setup of the firings performed during the HRE test campaign of Ambre is reported; as well as the methods adopted to retrieve the ballistic data.

3.1 Test facilities and instrumentation

The test campaign was performed in a vertical test bench. The configuration of the pressure-fed HRE system is sketched in Fig. 4. The engine consists of a single-port fuel grain with a conical post-combustion chamber and a graphite nozzle. The conical shape of the post-combustion thermal protection is dictated by the Ambre design. In a "test as you fly" logic, it has been decided to reproduce the same configuration of the autophagy Ambre rocket. Indeed, the motor is not provided of any pre-combustion chamber, since in the autophagy arrangement the catalyst bed assembly is directly em-

bedded inside the combustion chamber. Ignition is

Fig. 4: Test bench and instrumentation

achieved thanks to catalytic decomposition of 90% HTP through the catalyst bed. The mass flow rate of HTP (\dot{m}_{ox}) was commanded by an electrovalve that enabled the nitrogen (GN2) flow. The pressure level of GN2 was controlled by a pressure regulator. Calibration tests were performed in order to assess the pressure losses of the system and the GN2 pressure was set consequently to guarantee the desired \dot{m}_{ox} . The flow rate and the pressure of the oxidiser were measured through a digital flowmeter and a pressure sensor located immediately before the catalyst bed assembly.

To assess the temperature level of the recirculating hot gases in the top area of the engine, two thermocouples have been installed. The monitoring of the temperature in this zone is important to evaluate the environment that the catalyst bed and the insertion system (not used in this campaign) will face during burning.

The catalyst bed is designed to minimize the pressure losses and the potential hydrodynamic instabilities [5]. In total, the catalyst bed assembly consists of three main components: (i) the spray injector, (ii) the catalyser and (iii) the swirl injector. The catalyser consists of 2.7 mm alumina (Al_2O_3) pellets coated with manganese dioxide (MnO_2) starting from a sodium permanganate solution at 25% wt. The nominal L/D ratio of the catalyser is 0.34.

Once the liquid HTP is sprayed into the catalyser, the decomposed gas is directly injected, impinging the solid fuel in a swirling flow. This increases turbulence, mixing and residence time of hot gases [6]. To characterise the Swirling flow component, the geometrical swirl number (SN_g) is defined as

follows [7, 8]:

$$SN_g = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1 - (D_{hub}/D_{sw})^3}{1 - (D_{hub}/D_{sw})^2} \tan \alpha \quad (6)$$

The swirling injectors of this HRE were designed to produce $SN_{g1} = 4.95$ and $SN_{g2} = 2.40$. These values were chosen to span a range of achievable swirling flows.

Two pressure sensors were used to track the pressure evolution in the post combustion chamber. The collected pressure trace is used to retrieve the burning time τ_b and the ignition time τ_{ign} . The example in Fig.5 shows how these times are chosen. The ignition time of the solid fuel has been defined as the sum of the two different time spans τ_1 and τ_2 . As a convention for easy comparison of tests, the τ_1 interval starts from the initial instant at which the chamber pressure rises (t_{in}), and it finishes when the 70% of its maximum value is reached ($t_{CB,70\%}$). The τ_2 span is computed as the difference between the former instant and the time at which the chamber pressure reaches the 70% of its maximum ($t_{ign,70\%}$). Differently from the τ_1 computation, for τ_2 the maximum pressure is referred to the solid fuel combustion phase. Finally, the burn time τ_b is defined from the latter instant to the time at which the injection of GN2 starts to purge (t_{end}).

Fig. 5: Typical pressure trace of a combustion run (HRE_R4)

3.2 Data Reduction Technique

In order to characterise the behaviour of the combustion chamber, five different tests were carried out. Table I describes the characteristics that distinguish each test. The oxidiser flow rate \dot{m}_{ox} is defined as the nominal flow rate of the Ambre autophage engine. To vary the mass flow rate, the pressure of the peroxide skid is regulated according to the estimated losses of the line. A different SN_g has been obtained by changing the injection head

TABLE I: Description of test campaign HRE

Test ID	oxidiser Mass Flow	Swirl Number	Grooved Grain
HRE_R1	$0.90\dot{m}_{ox}$	4.95	×
HRE_R2	$1.30\dot{m}_{ox}$	2.40	×
HRE_R3	$0.60\dot{m}_{ox}$	4.95	×
HRE_R4	\dot{m}_{ox}	4.95	×
HRE_R5	\dot{m}_{ox}	4.95	✓

of the catalyst bed, causing a variation of the exit angle of the gas.

The grain of the last test (HRE_R5) features 4 straight grooves as in Fig. 6. These channels were made to simulate the real case where the grain is cut by the insertion system. Indeed, as can be seen in Fig. 1, the free-run stop of the screw-nut system is a set of four sharp beams called knives. This fifth test aims to estimate the impact of the grain's cut on the regression rate. However, it is not fully representative as it does not feature helical grooves due to the tapping by the screw.

Fig. 6: Grooved grain of the test HRE_R5 compared to other grains (not to scale)

3.2.1 Geometry-based and mass-based global regression rate data reduction

The regression rate of the solid fuel \dot{r}_f has been estimated with two different space- and time-averaged methods. The two methods base the \dot{r}_f evaluation on the variation of the port diameter occurred during firing:

$$\dot{r}_f = \frac{1}{\Delta t_b} \frac{D(t_{end}) - D(t_{in})}{2} \quad (7)$$

where $D(t_{in})$ is the initial port diameter measured by a caliper and Δt_b is the burning time. The difference between the two methods lies on the $D(t_{end})$ estimation. The mass-based method evaluates $D(t_{end})$ taking into account the mass variation Δm_f due to fuel consumption.

$$D(t_{end}) = \sqrt{D(t_{in})^2 + \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{\Delta m_f}{\rho L_f}} \quad (8)$$

where ρ and L_f are the density and the initial effective length (i.e., distance from injector to the end of the grain) of the fuel grain. On the other hand the geometry-based method (DD) involves a direct measurement of the final diameter by a caliper. The grain is cut in 4 quarters and the remaining thickness is measured with a calipers in the cuts at several axial positions. The $D(t_{end})$ of this method is then estimated by averaging the 4 thicknesses at a given axial position. For both methods the average oxidiser flow rate (\bar{G}_{ox}) was defined as the oxidiser mass flow rate divided by the average port area (\bar{A}_b):

$$\bar{G}_{ox} = \frac{\dot{m}_{ox}}{\bar{A}_b} = \frac{16\dot{m}_{ox}}{\pi [D(t_{end}) + D(t_{in})]^2} \quad (9)$$

Since the $D(t_{end})$ is evaluated in two different ways, slightly different values of \dot{r}_f and \bar{G}_{ox} are expected for the MB and DD approaches.

3.2.2 Local regression rate reduction

Cutting the grains in 4 parts and measuring the thickness allows to induce the local regression rate $\dot{r}_{f,x}$ along a distributed number of sections. The 4 measurements at each section are averaged to obtain a single thickness value $w_x(t_{end})$. Knowing the initial thickness of the grain $w(t_{in})$ and assuming it uniform along the axis, the local regression rate is retrieved as:

$$\dot{r}_{f,x} = \frac{w_x(t_{end}) - w(t_{in})}{\Delta t_b} \quad (10)$$

4 RESULTS

The outcomes of the ballistic analysis of the HRE test campaign are summarized in Tab. II, where the global regression rates have been evaluated according to the DD and the MB method. Unfortunately, the short combustion duration of HRE_R2 test does not allow to consider this test reliable. In fact, the discussion on the regression rate will not take into account the ballistic outcomes of HRE_R2. The uncertainties of the physical quantities in Tab. II have been assessed by considering the propagation of the measurements' errors.

Fig. 7 shows the local regression rate measurements of each test. For the sake of clarity, the curves exhibit a linear interpolation between each dimensionless axial value $\bar{x} = x/D(t_{in})$. The upstream temperature inside the combustion chamber has been reported as well. The trace of the thermocouples measurements are shown in Fig.8.

5 DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Regression Rate Analysis

Effect on the \dot{r}_f of variable G_{ox} was inspected. The Marxman's law has been retrieved by performing

TABLE II: Summary of the test campaign results

TEST ID	Ignition Time τ_{ign} [s]	Burning Time τ_b [s]	Chamber Pressure P_c [MPa]	Oxidizer Mass Flux		Regression Rate	
				$\bar{G}_{ox,DD}$ [kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	$\bar{G}_{ox,MB}$ [kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	$\dot{r}_{f,DD}$ [mm s ⁻¹]	$\dot{r}_{f,MB}$ [mm s ⁻¹]
HRE_R1	4.67	10.19	0.57 ± 0.03	24.5 ± 0.2	24.4 ± 0.2	0.44 ± 0.06	0.46 ± 0.05
HRE_R2	8.02	1.96	0.54 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-
HRE_R3	6.02	12.77	0.40 ± 0.05	16.6 ± 0.3	16.5 ± 0.3	0.34 ± 0.05	0.37 ± 0.07
HRE_R4	2.70	13.75	0.70 ± 0.02	27.4 ± 0.8	27.1 ± 0.8	0.50 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.06
HRE_R5	2.84	14.69	0.60 ± 0.03	27.8 ± 1.2	27.8 ± 1.2	0.42 ± 0.03	0.43 ± 0.07

Fig. 7: Local regression rate of each test

Fig. 8: Temperature evolution for each HRE test

a linear regression on the logarithmic form of the results of the two data reduction methods. Both the regressed curves exhibited coherent n values, respectively 0.70 (MB) and 0.71 (DD), confirming the legitimate proceedings followed for the DD method. Additionally, as it was expected, the MB regression rate showed a slightly greater a value than the DD (0.051 vs 0.047). Figure 9 shows the relative grading of the results. The HRE_R4 test showed the highest value among all the tests. Yet, this result gains much more interest when comparing it with

the HRE_R5 test. Both HRE_R4 and HRE_R5 have been performed at the same \bar{G}_{ox} , but a decrement of -16% in terms of $\dot{r}_{f,DD}$ turned out when adding longitudinal grooves. The root cause was not identified for certain. However, the local swirl angle (α_x) has been measured from traces on the internal surface of the grain to compare the two flows. With a definition inherited from Eq. 6 (i.e., $SN \propto \tan \alpha_x$), this method suggested that the local swirl number varies between these tests – the measurements show a decrement of -9% in terms of SN_g between HRE_R4 and HRE_R5. This result would lead to think that grooves might reduce the swirling intensity, acting like obstacles. The loss of momentum of the swirl component might have caused a lower convective heat transfer to the fuel, that in turn led to a lower regression rate. However, this thesis cannot be confirmed with so few results. It requires more investigation in future works.

 Fig. 9: $\dot{r}_{f,DD}(G_{ox})$ of the HRE test campaign

5.2 Upstream Temperature Measurements

The temperature measurements of the recirculating hot gases at the top area of the engine – around the catalyst bed – have been reported in Fig. 8. Several phenomena may influence this measurement. A non-uniform gap between the grain and the catalyst bed would lead to different cavity shapes around the catalyst bed, where the thermocouples are positioned. This probably happens as the grains used

are produced in large series and do not have strict tolerances. Thus, the intensity of recirculating flow structures in the upstream part of the chamber may vary between tests. To capture this, two different thermocouples were positioned at opposite sides of the engine. The lack of data from one of the thermocouples during each firing limits the observation of this phenomenon. This may explain the large difference between the temperatures traces. The measurements may be influenced also by the thermal dilatation of both catalyst bed and fuel grain. A simple dilatation model shows that the gap between the bed and the grain closes during a test, down to less than half the initial size, potentially preventing the hot gases to flow towards the sensor. In this context, the decreasing of the temperature in test HRE_R3, HRE_R4 and HRE_R5 might be explained. Yet, the continuous increasing temperature of tests HRE_R1 and HRE_R2 differ from the others. While this behaviour could be partially justified by the short duration of HRE_R2, the temperature steepness after few tenths of second of both tests significantly differ from the other tests. No definitive model is found to describe the temperature traces to this date. Nevertheless, a maximum temperature of about 760°C (HRE_R4) has been recorded. This temperature level is considered for the knives design in the autophage configuration, leading to the selection of steel as the constitutive material.

5.3 Fuel Ignition Time Analysis

The grain fuel heating time of each test is reported in Tab. II. The tests exhibited different ignition times, except for the similar outcomes of HRE_R4 and HRE_R5. The catalyst bed pressure raising times (τ_1) exhibited comparable values among all the tests. The fuel grain heating time (τ_2) varies more and it is considered the source of different ignition times (τ_{ign}). The work of Guo et al. [9] presented several fuel heating times as a function of oxidiser mass flux and decomposition temperature of the peroxide. No swirl injector was involved in that work, but similar trends were found. At constant decomposition temperature and low oxidiser mass flux, Guo observed a strong influence of oxidiser mass flux over the fuel heating time, which decreases with increasing G_{Ox} . The same behavior can be observed among tests HRE_R1, HRE_R3 and HRE_R4.

The HRE_R2 test has been performed with the highest oxidiser flow rate, nonetheless it showed the largest fuel heating time. This test was performed with a swirl injector featuring a lower geometrical swirl number. The delayed ignition can be explained by the smaller radial component of the flow out of the injector, which impinges the grain and causes a hot spot able to ignite. Wei et al.[10] investigated 90%HTP-PP with a catalyst bed and a swirl injector of swirl number equal to 3, in the same order as here. However, no jet directly impinges the grain in

that configuration. Even though the oxidiser mass flux was an order of magnitude higher and should logically lead to lower ignition times, the heating times in Wei's work resulted to match to the present paper outcomes. In this regard, the hypothesis on the impinging component enhancing τ_2 may find support.

Since the HRE_R4 and HRE_R5 test are the most representative tests for reproducing the operation of the Ambre rocket, the ignition time of these test are considered as a reference for the design. However, due to the insertion of the fuel in the autophage configuration, the hot spot under impingement constantly moves, potentially reducing the effective heat received by a particle of fuel. Therefore, the ignition time found in this campaign is considered as a minimum limit. The extent of this effect is yet to be tested in the autophage campaign. An additional igniter is envisaged to ensure ignition, should this effect be non-negligible.

5.4 Estimation of the Burning Grain Shape

Thanks to evaluation of the spatial-averaged and local regression rate, together with the ignition times of the HRE, it has been possible to estimate the regression length during its dynamic evolution and its equilibrium. Two runs of the developed code are reported in Figs. 10 - 11. In both these simulations, the insertion time is 15 s and the reference for the regression rates adopted (\dot{r}_f and $\dot{r}_{f,x}$) is the HRE_R5 test. The main difference between the two reproductions is the ignition time that varies from 5 to 10 s. The chosen ignition times represent a probable (5 s) and a pessimistic (10 s) case resulting from the discussion above. The initial slope of the conical grain is chosen to minimise the transition time to steady shape ($\theta_{in} = \theta_{eq}$).

Fig. 10: Evolution of fuel shape as a function of time for an insertion time of 15s with an ignition time of 5s using the experimental data of regression rate of test HRE_R5

In both cases, the insertion time is not enough to reach the equilibrium condition and the $L_{\dot{r},end}$ coincided with the $L_{\dot{r},max}$. It is important to comment that the faster the transition to the equilibrium condition, the lower the variations on the burning surface. This aspect is relevant to limit the O/F ratio shift during combustion and its impact on the

Fig. 11: Evolution of fuel shape as a function of time for an insertion time of 15s with an ignition time of 10s using the experimental data of regression rate of test HRE_R5

engine performances. The time required to achieve the equilibrium is not only affected by the matching between the cone slopes ($\theta_{in} = \theta_{eq}$), but it also depends on the estimation of the ignition time. In fact, the axial position of the grain with respect to the injector location before the insertion starts should be based on this parameter. As it is possible to see from both Fig. 10 - 11, the same initial conical shape reached a final configuration closer to the equilibrium one in the second simulation ($\tau_{ign} = 10$ s). Indeed, it can be concluded that the initial shape was more optimized for such ignition time, leading to a 6% gap rather than 20% of $L_{r,end}$ with respect to $L_{r,in}$.

6 FUTURE WORKS

6.1 Ambre Project

From these first tests of the combustion chamber, the Ambre rocket will be built progressively, implementing first the autophage version of the HRE, and then integrating flight systems. In particular, several test phases will allow to finish the characterisation of the components.

Inserting propellants into the pressurised combustion chamber with an embedded insertion system is a challenging task. The system currently developed by Alpha Impulsion is the only existing proposal to the authors' knowledge. Dry and wet insertion tests will be performed (Q2 2024), and they will allow the characterisation of the multiple effort types necessary to force the propellants into the pressurised engine. From this analysis, the nominal operating point for the first autophage firing tests will be chosen. The implementation of these "cold" insertion tests will be possible also thanks to the HRE test campaign. In fact, to validate the power balance of the embedded electric motor that powers the insertion system, the HRE test campaign results on chamber and catalytic bed pressure losses are needed.

Once the insertion system is characterised and integrated with the hybrid combustion chamber, autophage firing tests will be performed (Q2-Q3 2024).

A full static fire test of the autophage configuration will feature the same combustion subsystem analysed in this paper, with a lighter frame thanks to reduced thermal protection and closer to the flight configuration. An autophage engine has specific requirements for a test bench (see Fig. 12). The sliding fuel grain is used as a tank for the liquid oxidiser, which, must be inserted from the top interface. This interface is then closed and moves down during the test, inducing the use of flexible lines for the purge function notably.

Fig. 12: Autophage test bench configuration

Ambre is set to fly before the end of 2024. The main objective of this campaign is to prove that hybrid autophage propulsion can allow for take off. The influence of inertial loading of the vehicle on its behaviour will be observed, notably since static pressure due to acceleration tends to help propellant insertion, although this effect might not be noticeable in a small experimental rocket. Ambre will use the same architecture as the one shown in Fig.1, with the addition of fins and the recovery/telemetry systems.

6.2 Autophage Propulsion Maturation

Proving the viability of orbital autophage propulsion for a more affordable and cleaner access to space is an ambitious challenge that spans over many technical disciplines of chemical propulsion. Three research axes were identified, namely hybrid combustion, combustible launcher structures, and an efficient propellant insertion solution. The Ambre project is mainly focused on developing the third one with a first functional solution. Next phases of the maturation programme include scaling up this solution.

In hybrid combustion, autophage propulsion introduces sliding grains. Recent work implements them in a guided frame as a secondary fuel for bi-fluid combustion [3]. Alpha Impulsion proposes no guiding structure apart from the external chamber wall, to allow a classic hybrid combustion process on the internal surface of the port. This configuration will be observed for the first time in the Ambre project autophage firing tests (Q3 2024).

In the combustible structure axis, the modelling and simulation of the response to mechanical loads started in [1] shall continue, along with the characterisation of the mechanical and thermal properties of polymer materials of the structure in cryogenic temperatures associated with the liquid oxygen that should be used in the orbital launcher for performance.

7 CONCLUSION

The firing test campaign of an HRE using 90%HTP-HDPE is studied to validate components before the autophage engine configuration. The experimental regression rate shows a classical G_{ox} dependency, with the Marxman coefficient coherently computed with two different methods. The maximum temperature reached at the upper part of the engine due to the recirculating flows has been evaluated, driving the selection of the knives material. The ignition time shows a dependence on oxidiser mass flux, confirming previous outcomes in literature [9]. Additionally, a dependence on the swirl number and impingement intensity is also suggested. A model to compute the regression length is used as a reference to estimate the design of the combustion chamber of the autophage engine. The time dependent code shows a difference of less than 6% of regression length compared to the equilibrium state when the initial condition is optimised according to the ignition time. On the other hand, it shows a gap of more than 20% in case of an initial shape optimised for the wrong ignition time. Therefore, the estimation of the ignition time turns out to be an important parameter for the autophage configuration to properly design the combustion chamber length and to achieve a constant O/F ratio. For the autophage test campaign, the insertion duration will be limited so that a large ignition time would not lead to the grain hampering the electric motor. On the other end, a short ignition is handled by oversizing the combustion chamber's thermal protection thickness, which would not be protected by the grain. Thanks to this analysis the autophage engine configuration can then be designed and tested in the next phase of the Ambre project.

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